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A STUDY TO EVALUATE THE SOLAR ENERGY PRODUCT USAGE PRACTICES AND ITS SATISFACTION LEVEL AMONG THE CONSUMERS WITH REFERENCE TO COIMBATORE DISTRICT, TAMILNADU

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ABSTRACT

In India there is a demand for renewable source of energy in recent years. There is a necessary to measure the level of satisfaction of the solar energy product using consumers. To measure this, it is inherent to know the usage practices of those consumers. Solar energy is the major contributors to renewable energy next to Wind energy in Tamilnadu. There are many solar energy products available in the market which are used for various purposes at home and in society. The question is how far the consumers using solar energy products are satisfied with those products. The nature of product is identified and its duration of usage is measured. The respondents were also asked for the frequency and hours of usage of solar energy products. The increase in number of duration, frequency of usage, implies that the respondents are more informative about the products based on its pros and cons. When the respondents are using the products more frequently, it is easy to measure their level of satisfaction. The reason to measure the level of satisfaction among the solar energy product is to provide guidance to the future product users and also for the solar energy product manufacturing industries in framing policies accordingly.

Keywords: solar energy, consumers, solar policies, level of satisfaction

INTRODUCTION

This is a technology driven era. People use lots of technology in their day to day routine. Due to this behavior energy sources becomes scars and now they move towards using solar energy products for daily activities. Now a day’s people use solar energy products everywhere and it made their life easier and comfortable naturally. Solar energy products like power lights, automobiles, heaters and other gadgets are used in daily life. Even Railways, buses, airplanes, cars, etc are powered by solar energy. Recently ‘Solar Impulse2’, the solar powered aircraft has made its achievement in flying around the world. Even in Beijing, China solar buses are helping to reduce its carbon content in air. In Australia, ‘Solar Spirit’ model solar cars are gaining recognition in racing competitions around the world. With these advances there is no doubt that solar power is used not only for home appliances but also in transportation around the world. It not only saves the energy but also helps to leverage the solar energy in useful sectors around the world. It is required to measure the satisfaction level of the consumers using solar powered products to improve their satisfaction level and also improve the technology to make things easy.

Thus the main objective of this study is to see the level of satisfaction on solar energy products.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- To find out the duration of usage of the solar energy products by the consumers.
- To find out the frequency of usage of the solar energy products by the consumers.
- To find out the hours of usage of the solar energy products by the consumers.
- To find out the nature of the solar energy products used by the consumers.
- To find out the economic and social factors of level of satisfaction on usage of the solar energy products by the consumers.

CONTRIBUTION OF THE STUDY

This study has an impact on creating awareness about the satisfaction level among the consumers in the usage of the solar energy products. Because the study firstly analyse how much duration, frequency and hours does the consumers uses the solar energy products against the entire demographic variable which helps the manufacturers to find out the unaware area and to increase more satisfaction level for the solar energy products. Then the study focuses on economic and social factors involved in the usage of the solar energy products through which consumers are getting satisfied with the solar products. The result helps the decision makers to decide increase the usage of solar energy products by improving the lower satisfied factors and feel trust to use solar products for their own self.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Solar energy technology is a better one for consumers. Consumers are also expected to understand the importance of solar energy technology to encourage the solar energy product

sales (Gurubheemachar, 2017). Development and application of solar energy have been regarded by the government of India and common people who know that solar energy can provide more energy in future compare to other renewable energies. And government policies and initiatives should be improved to promote solar energy utilization in India (Sarat Kumar Sahoo, 2016). The companies producing solar energy products should follow the suggestions of the consumers so that they can reach the customers and boost up their sales enhancing their profits. Even educating the consumers about the solar energy products marketing will help companies to lift the economic status. There are evidence that there exist a gap between the perception of customers and the expectation level of the customers. Thus an understanding about the satisfaction level of the customers helps the managers to manage better customer relation (Shamsun Nahar Momotaz and Asif Mahbub Karim, 2012). A web based experiment was conducted where the respondents were asked to choose one out of three hypothetical electricity contracts. The result revealed that the preferences were made based on the integration of external control of heating, house hold electricity and information. It also shows that the result is influenced by the composition of house hold, age, gender and income. (Thomas Broberg , Lars Persson, 2016). A few studies concluded that solar power can be applied in a better way in hot desert environments with high solar radiation and high temperatures. There must be better government policies to help and develop large scale production. The study also states that funding should be provided for basic and applied research to promote development of solar power technology (S P Viswanathan, 2015). Even in automobile industry, solar power and electricity play a vital role. Due to hike in price of petrol and diesel, solar energy automobiles create a trend. And it is also user friendly (Prof.P.L.Chavan, GavandiMunirAkram, 2015).

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

To attain the objective of the study i.e. to find out the level of satisfaction among the consumers on the usage of solar energy products, firstly the duration of usage of solar energy products by the consumers is measured. Then the frequency and hours of usage of solar energy products by the respondents is identified. Based on the duration, frequency and hours of usage of the solar energy products, the level of satisfaction of the respondents can be measured. Then the perception on the solar energy product on the basis of its economic and social advantages is measured. It is important to find out on which economic or social factor is creating more satisfaction among the consumer on the usage of the solar energy products. This is important because the manufactures and the decision makers can focus on improving those factors which the customers are less satisfied to increase the overall level of satisfaction on the usage of the solar energy products. Thus the figure.1 shows the framework of the study to measure the level of satisfaction on solar energy products.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This is a descriptive research and an attempt to find out the satisfaction level of consumers relating to the usage of solar energy products. The data were collected from 400 consumers who use electrical, electronic and solar products in Coimbatore City. The responses were collected through issue of questionnaires. The research questionnaire included questions meant to collect demographic and other background information such as gender, age, qualification, marital status, Nature of family, Size of family and housing tenure.

Data Collection

The population chosen for this study is the consumers using solar energy product in Coimbatore city, Tamilnadu, India. The sample size for this study was determined based on the rules of thumb in order to obtain reliable and valid results. Kline (2010) suggested that a sample of 200 or larger is suitable for a complicated path model when the population is large. The sample size of 400 respondents meets the recommended guidelines of Kline 2010. A non probability sampling method i.e. convenience sampling is followed in this study, due to the large sample size needed in light of the limitations in time and level of accessibility to the population. Thus the respondents were selected on the basis of availability and willingness to participate in the survey. In order to attain the goals of this study i.e. to measure the level of satisfaction among the consumers about the usage of solar energy products, the questions in the scales were scored on a five point Likert scale ranging from 1 representing the strongest negative attitude towards the statement (very low awareness) to 5 representing the most positive attitude towards the statement (very high awareness). The demographic variables were all entered as categorical or ordinal values.

STATISTICAL RESULTS

Table 1: Consumers Duration of Usage of Solar Energy Products

Duration of usage	Frequency	Percent
less than 1 yr	70	17.5
1 to 3 yrs	142	35.5
4 to 5 yrs	122	30.5
above 5 yrs	66	16.5
Total	400	100

Source: Primary Data

It is noticed that about 35.5 percentages (142) of the respondents have used the solar energy products for one to three years. Then about 30.5 (122) percentage of the respondents have used the solar energy products for four to five years of durations. About 17.5 (70) percentage of the respondents have used the solar energy products only for less than one year. And only 16.5 (66) percentage of the respondents have used the solar energy products for more than five years.

Table 2: Nature of Solar Energy Products Used By the Consumers

Nature of product used	Frequency	Percent
solar lights	93	23.2
solar street lamp	176	44
solar power plant	8	2
solar invertors	8	2
solar car batteries	85	21.2
solar power generation systems	30	7.5
Total	400	100

Source: Primary Data

It is noticed that more number of respondents of about 44 (176) percentages have used the solar energy Street Lamps. Then about 23.2 (93) percentage of the respondents have used the solar

Lights and 21.2 (85) percentage of the respondents have used the solar Car Batteries. Only 7.5 (30) percentage of the respondents have used the solar power generation systems. Very less number of respondents of about 2 (8) percentage have used the solar Power Plant and Solar Invertors.

Table 3: Frequency of Usage of Solar Energy Products by the Consumers

Frequency of usage	Frequency	Percent
Always	169	42.2
Often	163	40.8
Sometime	25	6.2
Rarely	8	2
Necessary	35	8.8
Total	400	100

Source: Primary Data

It is noticed that 42.2 (169) percentage of the respondents have always used the solar energy products. And about 40.8 (163) percentage of the respondents have used the solar energy products very often. Respondents uses the solar energy products sometimes are 6.2 (25) percentage and only if necessary are 8.8 (35) percentage. Only 2 (8) percentage of the respondents are using the solar energy products very rarely.

Table 4: Hours of Usage of Solar Energy Products by the Consumers

Hours usage	Frequency	Percent
1	246	61.5
2	57	14.2
3	97	24.2
Total	400	100

Source: Primary Data

It is noticed that 61.5 (246) percentage of the respondents are using the solar energy products for one hour daily. About 24.2 (97) percentage of the respondents are using the solar energy

products for three hour daily. Only 14.2 (57) percentage of the respondents are using the solar energy products for two hour daily.

Table 5: Consumers Level of Satisfaction towards Usage of Solar Energy Products

Economic and Social factors		highly satisfied	satisfied	moderately satisfied	dissatisfied	highly dissatisfied
Generate more energy	frequency	117	193	58	32	0
	percentage	29.2	48.2	14.5	8	0
Greatest ability	frequency	125	153	90	32	0
	percentage	31.2	38.2	22.5	8	0
suited for roof top	frequency	141	177	34	40	8
	percentage	35.2	44.2	8.5	10	2
less maintenance	frequency	141	177	41	41	0
	percentage	35.2	44.2	10.2	10.2	0
long life features	frequency	141	153	74	32	0
	percentage	35.2	38.2	18.5	8	0
performance	frequency	125	169	66	40	0
	percentage	31.2	42.2	16.5	10	0
pollution free	frequency	157	153	58	32	0
	percentage	39.2	38.2	14.5	8	0
high efficiency	frequency	138	164	66	32	0
	percentage	34.5	41	16.5	8	0
durability	frequency	179	147	42	32	0
	percentage	44.8	36.8	10.5	8	0
valuable peak power	frequency	155	131	74	40	0
	percentage	38.8	32.8	18.5	10	0

Source: Primary Data

It is noticed that the customers are highly satisfied with the solar energy products on the basis of ‘pollution free’ (157), ‘Durability’ (179) and ‘Valuable peak power’ (155). And it is noticed that the respondents were satisfied with the solar energy products with regards to ‘Generate more

energy’ (193), ‘Greatest ability’ (153), ‘suited for roof top’ (177), ‘less maintenance’ (177), ‘long life features’ (153), ‘performance’ (169) and ‘high efficiency’ (164).

CONCLUSION

The main objective of the study is to measure the level of satisfaction of consumers on solar energy products and the result shows that most of the respondents are having awareness about the solar energy products. It is observed that respondents who have used the solar energy products for one to three years (142) are more and the respondents always (169) frequently uses the solar energy product for at least one hour (246) per day. Most of the respondents are using solar street lamp (176) when compared to the other solar energy products. The respondents were highly satisfied with the durability (179) of the solar energy product and are satisfied because it generates more energy (193). Thus it is concluded that customer level of satisfaction towards solar energy products is significantly influenced by their demographic, duration and frequency of usage, nature of product and socio-economic factors.

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